

Economic Instruments for Prevention and Control of Eutrophication

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Economic value of water has been assessed with reference to expansion of management schemes related to water resources. Restoring water quality in lakes and reservoirs and preventing pollution or any other kind of water degradation, have been examined from an economic viewpoint.

The concepts of water scarcity and economic value, as well as of externalities and other aspects associated with the allocation of water among uses and users, have been emphasized. Evidences have been presented on the economic impacts of eutrophication through the estimation of costs and benefits of reducing eutrophication or improving water quality in general. The evidences include different examples from the U.S.A., Europe, and developing countries.

The idea of economic instruments for prevention and control of eutrophication has been developed. Examples of implementation of taxes or effluent charges from selected European countries, U.S.A., Mexico, and Brazil have been cited. The

international practice shows that the effluent charges can be reasonably effective to improve water quality. It is suggested that the rates for the taxes or effluent charges need to be set at a sufficiently high level so they become a real incentive for abatement.

Information has also been provided on sound methodologies of benefit/cost analysis as a mechanism to evaluate or prioritize different initiatives of prevention and control of eutrophication, for restoration of eutrophic lakes and reservoirs and for improvement of water quality. Economic valuations of market and non-market resources, which are not treated within formal markets and/or that may have no price at all, have been discussed.

The results indicate that effective planning and management of lakes and reservoirs depend not only on a sound understanding of the physical and biological systems of these water bodies, but also of their value to people and the institutions that govern them. An understanding of economic benefits, costs, and policy instruments has been found vital for effective management.

References :

- **Garg, HK**; Garg, J (2010) Green House Effect on Biodiversity. *National Seminar on Integrated Management of Water Resources with Reference to Biodiversity and Livelihood*, 65.
- **Garg, HK**; Garg, J (2010) Prehistoric Indian Methods of Water Conservation. *National Seminar on Integrated Management of Water Resources with Reference to Biodiversity and Livelihood*, 58-59.
- **Garg, HK**; Garg, J (2009) Cyanobacterial Toxins. *National Symposium on Environmental Threat to Human Health in 21st Century*, Banaras Hindu University.
- **Garg, HK**; Garg, J (2007) Intricacies involved with detoxification of drinking water (Abs-18). *National Seminar on New Horizons in Toxicology and Sustenance of life*, 52.
- **Garg, HK** ; Garg, J (2002) Loss of biodiversity: Global perspective *National Symposium on Recent trends in Life Sciences, with reference to Wildlife & Conservation*.
- **Garg, HK**; Garg, J (2002) Biological heritage of India in jeopardy? *National Symposium on Recent trends in Life Sciences, with reference to Wildlife & Conservation*.
- **Garg, HK**; Garg, J (2002) Eutrophication trends in Bhopal waters: A microcosmal approach. *National Seminar on Waste Water Management: Pollution Preventions in Perspective of Prospective Features*, 24.
- **Garg, HK**; Garg, J (2002) Statistical relationship between eutrophication causing nutrients & phytoplankton. *National Seminar on Environment Toxicology*, 4/4.
- **Garg, HK**; Garg, J (1999) Effect of inorganic phosphorus on algae excised from inland waters. **Indian Journal of Zoological Spectrum**, **9(1/2)**: 1-3.
- **Garg, HK** (1999) Extinction of Dinosaurs. Lecture delivered during VIII Refresher Course in Zoology. Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.
- **Garg, HK**; Garg, J (1998) Impact of magnesium acetate on algae in experimental hydrosystems. *National Seminar on Inter-disciplinary Areas of Science & Technology: Present & Future*, 24.
- **Garg, HK**; Garg, J (1997) Bhopal waters -Heading towards extinction? *National Research Seminar on Conservation of Aquatic Resources*, 33-34.
- **Garg, HK** ; Jain, OP; Garg, J (2006) Algal succession in nutrient enriched biocoenosis. *M.P. Science Congress* 14.
- **Garg, HK** ; Tejraj, MK; Jain, OP (2002) Microphyte toxins: Impact on aquatic life. *National Seminar on Biodiversity & Sustainable Use of Bioresources*, 41-42.
- Garg, J; **Garg, HK** (2007) Bioactive Toxins (LS-85). *International Congress of Environmental Research*, 3449.
- Garg, J; **Garg, HK** (2007) Effect of agro-nutrients on aquatic flora (Abs-12). *National Seminar on New Horizons in Toxicology and Sustenance of life*, 45-46.
- Garg, J; **Garg, HK** (2006) Applicability of nutrient monitoring for managing eutrophication in sub tropics. *National Symposium on Recent trends in Life Sciences*.
- Garg, J; **Garg, HK** (2003) Bioassay response to additions of urea in simulated lake environments. **Pollution Research**, **21(3)**: 463-466.

- Garg, J; **Garg, HK** (2003) Algae as indicators of eutrophication : A microcosmal approach. **Environment & Ecology, 21(2):** 313-316.
- Garg, J; **Garg, HK** (2003) Nutrient phytoplankton relationships in some hypereutrophic Central Indian reservoirs. **Journal of Ecotoxicology & Environmental Monitoring, 13 (1):** 21-27.
- Garg, J; **Garg, HK** (2002) Nutrient loading and its consequences in a lake ecosystem*. **Tropical Ecology 43 (2):** 355-358. (1.482)
- Garg, J; **Garg, HK** (2001) Impact of phosphorus on hydrobiology of Bhopal waters : A microcosmal study. **Journal of Ecotoxicology & Environmental Monitoring, 11(4):** 271-277.
- Garg, J; **Garg, HK** (2001) Water Quality Management Strategies for Conservation of Bhopal Waters. **Environmental Conservation Journal, 2(2/3):** 101-104. (0.5800)
- Garg, J; **Garg, HK** (2002) Water quality management strategies for conservation of Bhopal waters-II. *National Seminar on Waste Water Management: Pollution Preventions in Perspective of Prospective Features, 12/38.*
- Garg, J; **Garg, HK** (1997) Microcosmal studies in connection with restoration of Bhopal waters. *National Research Seminar on Conservation of Aquatic Resources, 37-38.*
- Garg, J; **Garg, HK** (1997) Impact of agricultural nutrients on algal diversity. *National Symposium on Biodiversity, 10.*
- **Garg, J** ; Garg, HK; Khan, JA (2002) Flos-aquae in potable waters: Remedies to counteract intoxication. *National Seminar on Biodiversity & Sustainable Use of Bioresources, 35.*
- **Garg, J** ; Garg, HK; Bharadwaj, AK (2002) Freshwater scums: Aftermath on human beings. *National Seminar on Biodiversity & Sustainable Use of Bioresources, 36-37.*
- **Garg, J** ; Garg, HK; Adholia, UN (2002) Myxophycean blooms in lentic habitats. *National Seminar on Biodiversity & Sustainable Use of Bioresources, 40.*